

**A STUDY OF BACK STRENGTH IN ELITE INDIAN MALE VOLLEYBALL PLAYERS:
IN ASSOCIATION WITH SELECTED ANTHROPOMETRIC VARIABLES AND
PERFORMANCE TESTS**

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ABSTRACT

Objectives: The purpose of the present study was to examine back strength in elite Indian male volleyball players and assess its association with selected anthropometric variables and performance tests. **Methods:** To achieve this objective, four anthropometric variables, such as, height, weight, BMI, and right lower-extremity length along with two body-composition components, such as percent body fat and percent lean body mass were assessed. In addition, three performance tests, such as, the sit-and-reach test, the Illinois agility test, and the vertical jump test together with back strength were measured in a randomly selected sample of 88 elite Indian male volleyball players aged 18–25 years. A comparable control group (n = 93) from the same location was also included for comparative analysis. **Results:** The results indicated that Student's *t*-test revealed significant differences ($p \leq 0.006$ – 0.001) in all measured variables between volleyball players and controls. Among the male volleyball players, back strength showed significant positive correlations ($p \leq 0.003$ – 0.001) with height, weight, right lower-extremity length, percent lean body mass, Illinois agility test performance, and vertical jump performance, while a significant negative correlation ($p \leq 0.005$) was observed only with percent body fat. **Conclusion:** In conclusion, back strength demonstrated strong positive associations with three anthropometric traits, one body composition component, and three performance tests in elite Indian male volleyball players.

KEYWORDS: Back strength, Anthropometric variables, Body composition components, Performance tests, Elite Indian male volleyball players.

INTRODUCTION

Volleyball is an intermittent sport that requires athletes to perform frequent short bursts of high-intensity activity interspersed with periods of low-intensity movement.^[1,2] These repeated high-intensity efforts, combined with the overall duration of a match, demand well-developed aerobic and anaerobic a-lactic (ATP-CP) energy systems.^[3] Consequently, volleyball players must possess high levels of speed, agility, upper- and lower-body muscular power, and maximal aerobic capacity.^[2]

Muscular strength, endurance, and flexibility are essential components of healthy back function.

Numerous studies have emphasized the critical role of muscle strength in overall health and well-being.^[4-7] Several external factor, such as altitude^[8], posture during exertion^[9], and diet^[10], as well as internal factors—including age, sex^[11], height, and weight^[12], influence the maximum force a muscle can produce.^[13]

Across various playing positions in volleyball, substantial back muscle strength is required. Mechanical factors contribute significantly to the development of degenerative processes and lumbar spine injuries. Understanding the maximal capacity of the back muscles is necessary for assessing endurance and fatigue under

match conditions.^[14] However, because the anatomical and biomechanical structures of the back are highly complex, accurately measuring back muscle strength outside a research environment is challenging. Establishing relationships between back strength and easily measurable anthropometric or performance variables could enable coaches and trainers to make reliable field-based estimations.

Although several studies have explored the anthropometric and physiological characteristics of volleyball players^[15,16], information on back strength and its association with anthropometric variables remains limited, particularly in the Indian context. Therefore, the present study was undertaken to address this gap.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Participants

The present cross-sectional study was conducted on a randomly selected sample of 88 elite Indian male volleyball players aged 18–25 years (mean age 22.01 ± 2.23), who participated in the 2023 Inter-University Male Volleyball Competition held at Kurukshetra University, Haryana, India. The participating teams represented Punjabi University, Patiala; Panjab University, Chandigarh; Guru Nanak Dev University, Amritsar; Kurukshetra University, Kurukshetra; Himachal Pradesh University, Himachal Pradesh; and the University of Delhi, Delhi.

A control group comprising 93 individuals (mean age 22.01 ± 1.97) without any formal athletic background was also recruited from the same venue for comparative purposes. Ages were verified using official records from the respective institutions. Written informed consent was obtained from all participants. Data collection was carried out under natural environmental conditions in the morning hours between 8:00 AM and 12:00 noon. The study protocol was approved by the local ethics committee.

Anthropometric Measurements

A total of four anthropometric variables—height (HT), weight (WT), BMI, and right lower-extremity length (RLEL)—along with two body composition components—percent body fat (%BF) and percent lean body mass (%LBM)—one physical parameter, back strength (BS), and three performance tests—the sit-and-reach test (S&RT), Illinois agility test (IAT), and vertical jump test (VJT)—were assessed for each participant.

Anthropometric measurements were obtained using standard procedures^[17] and recorded in triplicate, with the median value used for analysis. Height was measured during inspiration using a stadiometer (Holtain Ltd., Crymych, Dyfed, UK) to the nearest 0.1 cm, while weight was recorded using a digital standing scale (Model DS-410, Seiko, Tokyo, Japan) to the nearest 0.1 kg. BMI was calculated as weight (kg)/height² (m²). Right lower-extremity length was measured vertically

from the iliospinale posterior landmark to the floor using an anthropometer, recorded in centimeters.

Percent body fat was estimated from skinfold measurements at four sites—biceps, triceps, subscapular, and suprailiac—taken with a Harpenden skinfold caliper (Holtain Ltd., Crosswell, Crymych, UK) to the nearest 0.2 mm and calculated using the Durnin and Womersley equation.^[18] Percent lean body mass was derived by subtracting percent body fat from 100.

Back Strength Measurement (BS)

Back strength was assessed using a back–leg–chest dynamometer. After a three-minute self-directed warm-up, each participant was positioned upright with the knees slightly bent so that the hands could grasp the handle at an appropriate height. The subject then extended the knees and applied pulling force on the handle by lifting the dynamometer chain. For the measurement, the body was inclined forward at approximately 60 degrees. Back muscle strength was recorded from the dynamometer dial, with the best of three trials (in kilograms) used for analysis. A 30-second rest interval was provided between successive trials.

Sit and Reach Test (S&RT)

Participants were instructed to complete an adequate warm-up before performing the sit-and-reach test. Seated on the floor with their feet placed flat against the inner surface of the testing box, they positioned one hand over the other with the middle fingertips aligned. They then slowly reached forward along the 20-inch scale, avoiding any bouncing or jerking movements, and extended as far as possible. The test was performed three times, and the best value was recorded in inches.

Illinois Agility Test (IAT)

Before the test began, each subject completed a thorough warm-up and then positioned himself face down at the starting line, with the head oriented toward the “start,” legs extended, feet together, and arms resting at the sides. At the command, the participant rose quickly to his feet and navigated the agility course around the cones, moving as rapidly as possible toward the “finish” point. The total time from the starting command to crossing the finish line was recorded as the trial score. Three trials were performed, and the best time, measured in seconds to two decimal places, was used for analysis.

Vertical Jump Test (VJT)

A proper warm-up consisting of several light jumps was completed, followed by a brief rest period, during which the subject’s jumping technique was reviewed. Participants were instructed to perform a countermovement—bending the knees immediately before the jump—to activate the stretch–shortening cycle and enhance lower-limb power production.

Before attempting the vertical jump, each subject stood sideways to a wall and reached upward as high as

possible with feet flat on the floor to determine the standing reach height. When ready, and with color applied to the distal phalanx of the right middle finger, the subject executed a maximal vertical jump using both the arms and legs for propulsion and touched the wall at the highest point reached.

Multiple attempts were allowed, with short rest intervals, until performance plateaued or declined. The best jump height was recorded in centimeters, and the net vertical jump height was calculated by subtracting the standing reach height from the maximum jump height.

Statistical Analysis

Standard descriptive statistics (mean \pm standard deviation) were calculated for all measured and derived variables. Student's t-test was employed to compare data between elite Indian male volleyball players and controls. Pearson's correlation coefficients were computed to examine relationships among the measured variables. All analyses were performed using SPSS (Statistical Package for the Social Sciences) version 23.0, with statistical significance set at the 5% level.

RESULTS

Table 1 presents the descriptive statistics for back strength, selected anthropometric variables, body composition components, and performance tests in elite Indian male volleyball players and controls. Comparison between the two groups revealed statistically significant differences ($p \leq 0.046$ – 0.001) across all measured variables (Fig. 1).

Pearson's correlation coefficients for back strength with the selected anthropometric traits, body composition components, and performance tests are shown in Table 2. Back strength demonstrated significant positive correlations ($p \leq 0.003$ – 0.001) with height (HT), weight (WT), BMI, right lower-extremity length (RLEL), percent lean body mass (%LBM), Illinois agility test (IAT) performance, and vertical jump test (VJT) performance. A significant negative correlation ($p \leq 0.005$) was observed only with percent body fat (%BF) in the volleyball players.

Table 1: Descriptive statistics of various anthropometric variables, body composition components and performance tests in elite Indian male inter-university volleyball players.

Variables	Volleyball males (n=88)		Control males (n=93)		t-value	p-value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD		
HT (cm)	182.32	5.64	170.55	4.38	11.301	<0.001
WT (kg)	77.21	4.33	68.73	4.62	7.367	<0.001
BMI (kg/m ²)	23.86	4.32	22.64	3.89	2.982	<0.046
RLEL (cm)	107.25	5.48	99.04	4.96	4.575	<0.001
%BF	19.37	4.37	22.52	5.71	3.852	<0.001
%LBM	80.63	4.37	77.48	4.52	3.743	<0.001
S&RT (inches)	13.41	3.74	7.89	5.21	4.141	<0.001
IAT (sec.)	14.09	3.33	17.54	4.79	3.968	<0.001
VJT (cm)	51.98	5.74	43.03	5.95	6.786	<0.001
BS (kg)	166.42	6.47	125.63	6.89	9.741	<0.001

HT=Height; WT=Weight; BMI=Body mass index; RLEL= Right lower extremity length; %BF=Percent body fat; %LBM=Percent lean body mass; S&RT=Sit & reach test; IAT= Illinois agility test; VJT= Vertical jump test and BS=Back strength

Fig. 1: Comparison of mean values between Volleyball players and Controls.

Table 2: Pearson's correlation coefficients of back strength with selected anthropometric variables, body composition components and performance tests in elite Indian male inter-university volleyball players.

Variables	Volleyball males (n=88)	
	R-value	P-value
Height (cm)	0.574	<0.001
Weight (kg)	0.687	<0.001
Body mass index (kg/m ²)	0.354	<0.003
Right lower extremity length (cm)	0.763	<0.001
Percent body fat	-0.352	<0.005
Percent lean body mass	0.431	<0.003
Sit & reach test (inches)	0.362	<0.002
Illinois agility test (sec.)	0.538	<0.001
Vertical jump test (cm)	0.653	<0.001

DISCUSSION

In volleyball, where players frequently handle the ball above head level, height is considered a critical physical attribute. In the present study, the mean height of the male players (182.32 ± 5.64 cm) was higher than that reported for male volleyball players from West Bengal, India (173.10 ± 4.19 cm)^[19], but lower than the mean height of English players (191.00 ± 5.0 cm).^[20] The significantly greater body weight observed among the players in this study may be a disadvantage for achieving optimal jumping height, as a heavier body mass requires more force to lift.

Elite Indian male volleyball players exhibited significantly higher back strength values than their control counterparts, likely due to regular physical activity and rigorous training regimens. Back strength demonstrated significant positive correlations ($p < 0.003$ – 0.001) with all variables examined, except percent body fat (%BF), which showed a significant negative correlation. These findings suggest that the measured anthropometric and performance variables contribute meaningfully to back strength in volleyball players. Given that jumping and landing actions require substantial back strength, well-developed back musculature plays an essential role in both elevating the body during jumps and ensuring safe, controlled landings.

Accurate assessment of back strength is important for reducing sport-specific injuries and enhancing performance. Training programs should therefore incorporate targeted back-strengthening exercises according to the needs of the players. The results of the present study are consistent with earlier findings in elite Indian cricketers^[21], field hockey players^[7], Indian adolescents^[8], and physical laborers^[7], all of which reported strong positive associations between back strength and selected anthropometric parameters.

Body composition also plays a key role in influencing strength and skill in various sports.^[24] In line with previous findings by Tsunawake et al.^[25] and Filaire et al.^[26], volleyball players in the present study exhibited lower percent body fat than controls, likely due to regular training and sustained physical activity.

The main limitations of this study include a relatively small sample size and the inclusion of only male participants. Future research should aim to address these limitations by incorporating larger and more diverse samples.

CONCLUSION

The findings of the present study indicate that significant differences were observed in all measured variables between elite Indian male volleyball players and controls. Among the volleyball players, back strength showed significant positive correlations with all variables assessed, except for percent body fat, which demonstrated a significant negative correlation. The results of this study have important practical implications and may be valuable for talent identification in volleyball, as well as for designing and refining sport-specific training programs.

Declaration by Authors: The authors hereby declared that it was their original piece of research and had not been sent to any other journal for publication.

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Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts of interest.

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